

LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE CORRUGATED CORE SANDWICH PANELS: EFFECT OF IMPACTOR GEOMETRY

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Abstract

Fibre reinforced polymer composite sandwich structures are exceedingly using for engineering applications requiring low-weight, high strength/stiffness, and protection from collision events. In this study, an experimental program was conducted to investigate the influence of the impactor shapes on the impact behaviour and failure mechanisms of the trapezoidal composite corrugated core sandwich structures under the low-velocity impact. The composite sandwich panels were fabricated by using woven E-glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite. The experiments were carried out employing drop-weight test machine with four different shaped steel impactor heads, i.e., flat, large and small hemispherical, and conical at 23J of kinetic energy. The results revealed that the impact behaviour of the composite corrugated sandwich significantly influenced by the impactor head. The de-bonding damage mode of the upper skin and the corrugated core dominated with different impactor heads. The flat impactor head has caused external damage mode on the upper face sheet, while core failure mode and fibre break at impacted area have caused by small hemispherical and conical impactor heads, respectively.

1. Introduction

Sandwich structures, comprising of lightweight core materials bonded to stiff and strong upper and lower face sheet, are obtaining increasing employment in a wide range of engineering [1-5] applications. These sandwich core structures offer superior advantages [6-8], particularly when compared to the monolithic plates of the same materials. Although the sandwich systems have shown significant resistant to external impact loads such as low-velocity impact, complete impact behaviour is not well understood. It is a sound judgment that of such sandwiches are prone to undergo impact events from different shapes and geometries of foreign objects during their operations of assembly, maintenance, and period of service [9, 10]. The shape of the impactors might influence the impact responses and damage modes of such sandwich structures. As a consequence, it is necessary to consider the influence of the impactor shape on responses and damage modes of the composite sandwich panels under the low-velocity impact. In addition, such damage and failures may significantly reduce the stiffness and residual strength of the composite structures, possibly producing catastrophic failure of the composite sandwich panels.

Numerous research, have been performed on the impact response of the corrugated core sandwich panels, and most of the studies have focused on metallic structures. For example, Tilbrook et al. [11] investigated the out-of-plane dynamic response of the corrugated steel core and Y-frame core sandwich panels under low-velocity impact loading. They addressed that the foremost strengthening mechanism of the sandwich was the inertial stabilization of the core member under the low-velocity impact. The dynamic/impact behaviour of steel corrugated core and Y-frame beam sandwich also

investigated by Rubino et al.[12], and they have suggested that sandwich beams with a longitudinal core orientation had an effective impact response performance than their monolithic counterparts.

In recent years much work on the fibre reinforced polymer composite sandwich panels have been reported in the literature. Unfortunately, only a few studies have given details on the dynamic/impact response of such sandwich structures. The dynamic strengthening effect of the E-glass composite corrugated sandwiches has been investigated by Russell et al.[13], and they have suggested that foam filling as a sandwich core has not shown any significant influence on the impact response of the structure. Schneider et al. [14] investigated the out-of-plane dynamic behaviour of reinforced composite corrugated core sandwich structure, which is made from a fully recyclable self-reinforced polymer (SrP) composites. The results revealed that (SrP) corrugated cores had a superior impact behaviour compared with traditional polymeric foams. Liu, et al. [15] investigated the effect of impactor shape on hybrid corrugated core sandwich structures response under the low-velocity impact. They have suggested that the composite upper face sheet exhibited fibre damage, and the buckling of aluminium core members depends on the impactor shape. Boonkong, et al. [16] investigated low-velocity impact response of light-weight curvilinear-core sandwich panel, and they have reported that the perforation energy increased with the increase of impactor head diameter due to increases of the area of fractured material.

To the authors knowledge, there is no significant research on impactor shape on the fibre reinforced sandwich structures available in literature. It is obvious that the impactor shapes can affect the impact response and damage mechanisms of sandwich structures because in the realty impact events the impactor heads have different shape and geometry, such debris, dropped tools during maintenance service, hail storm. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate the effect of impactor geometry on the low-velocity impact response of the trapezoidal composite corrugated core sandwich structure. The experimental programs were conducted by using flat, large and small hemispherical, and conical impactor noses.

2. Experimental procedure

A trapezoidal E-glass/fibre reinforced epoxy composite corrugation core sandwiches were manufactured by utilising a simple compression moulding technique. A woven E-glass/fibre (0/90) and epoxy matrix were used to fabricate the sandwich specimens. Hand lay-up technique was used to fabricate the skins and corrugated core. The sample left at 25 °C for 48 hours to cure then they demoulded. Next, the parts bonded together by using Technigluue (100%R5 and 25%H5) to construct unit cells of the corrugated sandwich. Finally, the specimens cut and finished to the required geometry. Fig.1 (a) shows the schematic profile of the trapezoidal corrugated core sandwich. Table 1 shows the geometric parametrise o the corrugated core sandwich.

Drop-weight impact tower (Fig.1b) was used to conduct low-velocity impact tests by utilizing four different types of striker heads (Fig.1c). The sandwich specimen was mounted horizontally and clamped along two sides only by jaw clamp. The constant kinetic energy of 23J was employed; this value of impactor energy is slightly above the threshold value of damaged energy of the composite based ASTM D7136 standard. The corrugated specimen was impacted on the short span. The dimension and the geometry of the impactor head are shown in Fig.1c. Simen's LMS SCADAS data acquisition system was employed to acquire the data. In order to get force response, the piezoelectric load cell (PCB 200C20) was set in between the impactor load and impactor head. Finally, the acquired data were stored for analysing.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of the cross-section of the trapezoidal composite corrugated core sandwich, (b) drop-weight system, and (c) profile of the impactor heads.

Table 1. The parametric geometry of woven E-GFR composite corrugated core configuration.

L_1 (mm)	L_c (mm)	H (mm)	t_c (mm)	t_u & t_l (mm)	w
38	34.6	24.5	1.35	1.85	45

Note: The table shows the average value of four corrugated sandwiches dimensions.

3. Results and discussion

The low-velocity impact was conducted on the trapezoidal composite corrugated core structures with different impactor shapes. Fig.2 shows the force-time response of the sandwich structures, and it can be observed that the force-time curves exhibited evident variation with different geometries of impactor head. The evolution of the peak force also depended on the various impactor geometries. From the figure, it can be seen very clearly that the impactor having a larger contact surface produced higher force resistance due to minimal local damage of the impacted area, which led to resist the

impact force by the core struts. The sandwich curve responses with the hemistichal revealed to stage due to elastic buckling of the core struts. However, the small contact between the pointer impactor head and the sandwich skin caused to decrease the contact stiffness parameter and increase damage area; thus, the force peak load showed minimum resistance and impact duration. It can be inferred that the impact response of the trapezoidal composite corrugated core sandwich significantly depends on the impactor shape.

Figure 2: The force-time response of TCS under low-velocity impact event.

4. Damaged modes

A visible damage evaluation was performed to gain more information about the impact damage mode, which originated due to different impactor heads. Fig.3 shows that the different impactor geometries result in various failure modes. Barely visible impact damage (BVID) caused by the flat and hemispherical head (blunt) and occurred in a more impacted area on the top skin sheet (Fig.3a-c). However, the damage mode caused by the conical was clearly visible impact damage (CVID), which incorporated fibre breakage and matrix crack, as shown in Fig.3 (d).

The side view of the impacted sandwiches has shown that the de-bonding of the upper face sheet with corrugated core was the dominated failure mode of flat impactor head (Fig.4a-b). In contrast, failures resulting from the small-hemispherical and conical have a severe failure of the core angle and localised profound failure of the skin of the sandwich, respectively (Fig.4c-d). It can be concluded that although the impact energy was constant, the different impactor heads caused different damage mode with including external and internal failure.

Figure 3: The damaged mode of upper face sheet: (a) flat head; (b) large hemispherical head; (c) small hemispherical head; (d) conical head.

Figure 4: Damaged mode of the cross-section of the impacted sandwich (a) flat head, (b) large hemispherical head, (c) small hemispherical head, and (d) conical head.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the effect of the impactor geometry on the low-velocity impact response of composite corrugated core sandwich structures fabricated by glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite face sheets is experimentally investigated. Dynamic low-velocity impact tests were performed to make clear the effects of impactor geometry on the impact force and damage modes. Based on the outcome, the following conclusions can be inferred:

- The flat impactor head has caused less damages to the sandwich structure.
- Non-perforation has been showed with flat and hemispherical heads; in contrary, the top face sheet exhibited a semi-perforation with conical impactor head.
- The de-bonding was dominated as the internal failure mode for most of the impactor heads.

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